

To Compare the Performance of YO-YO Intermittent Recovery Test Level-1 in Recreational Basketball and Cricket Players

Mumux Mirani^{1*}, Amisha Kapopara², Sonal Rathod³, Aparna Bachkaniwala⁴

^{1,2,3,4}SPB Physiotherapy College (Veer Narmad South Gujarat University, Surat-395004, Gujarat, India.

*Corresponding Author - mumuxmirani@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE: Yo-Yo intermittent tests are frequently used in a variety of sports and research studies to determine physical fitness. Specifically, the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test was a valid measure of fitness performance in the manner of total covered distance in meters, maximum oxygen consumption in VO_2 Max and levels achieved which is set in the way of increasing speed in kilometer/hour with decreasing time in seconds to accelerate the test to measure and calculate the outcomes of the test. The purpose of the study is to compare the result of fitness ability using Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test level 1 between recreational basketball and cricket players. This study helped to measure an individual's ability to repeatedly perform intervals over a prolonged period of time.

METHOD: Participants were explained the procedure and informed consent obtained. 68 participants who were recreational players were taken. Out of which 34 were cricket and 34 were basketball players. YYIRT 1 test was performed on them. The test was continued till the participant could continue the test or if the participant gets 2 warning signals simultaneously for not reaching the end point till the beep rings and then it was stopped. Outcome measures used were total distance covered and VO_2 max which was compared between 2 groups.

Result: This study showed that there is no significant difference in performance i.e., total distance covered and VO_2 max. between recreational cricket and basketball players.

Conclusion: This study shows equal effectiveness in both recreational cricket and basketball players.

Keywords: YYIR test level 1, Total covered distance, VO_2 Max, Cricketers, Basketball players

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the introduction of the Yo-Yo Intermittent (YYI) test as a field test method in the 1990s, an evolution of the Yo-Yo test family has occurred¹. Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test is the field test method which is having repeated shuttles in pre-measured field with recovery phase in it where the person/runner is set to be recovered from shuttle and get ready for the next shuttle. Today, Yo-Yo test variants are extensively used to assess physical fitness in different sports and populations.^{1,2}

The test was developed in the 1990s by the Danish soccer physiologist Jens Bangsbo and his colleagues.³

There are three variations of the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test: level 1, level 2 and the sub-maximal test. These variations contain Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1, Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 2, Yo-Yo intermittent endurance test level 1, Yo-Yo intermittent endurance test level 2, Yo-Yo endurance test level 1 and lastly, Yo-Yo endurance test level 2.⁴

The Yo-Yo intermittent recovery level 1 (YYIR1) focuses on an individual's ability to repeatedly perform high-intensity aerobic work.⁵ The Yo-Yo intermittent recovery level 2 (YYIR2) test examines the capacity to perform intense intermittent exercise with a large anaerobic component in combination with a significant aerobic contribution.⁶

The sub-maximal yo-yo intermittent recovery test was developed as a method of monitoring performance during competitive periods (e.g., in-season), injury rehabilitation, or individuals who may struggle with performing the maximal tests.^{4,7} Here we are focusing on the yo-yo intermittent recovery test level 1.

The Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test Level 1 test was developed to measure an athlete's ability to repeatedly perform high-intensity aerobic work.^{1,8} Since then, it has established itself as one of the most commonly used aerobic field tests for youth and recreational athletes.⁹

VO₂ Max is the maximum or optimum rate at which the heart, lungs and muscles can effectively use oxygen during exercise, used as a way of measuring a person's individual aerobic capacity. It has been shown to be a valid and reliable predictor of high-intensity aerobic capacity and VO₂ Max amongst athletes from various sports and competition-levels.⁶

The YYIR1 is designed for young or recreational athletes who possess lower aerobic capacity – this level begins at 10km/hr. Performances in the YYIR tests for young athletes have also been shown to improve with increases in age.^{3, 4, 5, 6} However, this may be more specifically related to biological maturity rather than chronological age though it is debatable even the maximum oxygen consumption regarding the fitness levels with the age factor are also sometimes debatable.^{9, 10}

Regardless, YYIR tests have also been demonstrated to be a more sensitive measure of performance changes than maximum oxygen uptake (VO₂ max). Furthermore, as relationships between sub-maximal YYIR test performance and heart rate had been observed.

Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test Level 1 involves running between two markers 20 meters apart, following audio cues which dictate the running speed required. After each 40 meters run, the participants have an active break of 10 seconds before running 40 meters again. At regular intervals, the required running speed increases. The test continues until the participants are no longer able to keep up with the required pace.^{11, 12}

The yo-yo test was developed primarily for football (soccer) players,^{1,2} though is becoming a popular test for many team sport athletes, with even the Indian cricket team using it as a selection criterion. The Australian football draft combine have replaced the beep test on their testing program with the yo-yo test, and we may see this happen more as the yo-yo test is seen more specific for the intermittent type field running sports.

Reliability: Reliability would depend on how strictly the test is run, and the previous practice allowed for the subject.⁹

Moreover, even a test with sufficient validity and reliability will still have some degree of error/inconsistency, but understanding how much is a crucial part of the data analysis.⁹

The YYIR1 has been repeatedly proven as a valid and reliable tool with high-reproducibility for measuring high-intensity aerobic capacity amongst athletes from various sports and

competition-levels.^{10, 11, 12, 13}

Furthermore, the YYIR1 has also been shown to be a moderately reliable predictor of maximal oxygen uptake (VO₂ Max).⁶

The good performance and better results in YYIR test level 1 can be achieved by understanding the test properly, repeating intermittent running practice, resistance training, high-intensity interval training. Technical training regarding with the beep sound shuttle running test and weekly test sessions will also help to improve physical ability and fitness in the body and mental awareness. It helps to evaluate the different physical capacities in individuals and their sensitivity to training under the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1.¹³

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

- 1. STUDY DESIGN:** Cross Sectional Observational Study
- 2. SAMPLING DESIGN:** Random Sampling
- 3. STUDY SETTING:** Lalbhai Contractor Cricket Stadium and Coaching Academy
: Adajan Sports Complex

4. **SAMPLE SIZE:** 68 participants
34 Recreational Basketball players
34 Recreational Cricket players

5. **AGE GROUP:** 18 to 30 years.

6. **STUDY DURATION:** 6 months.

7. **MATERIALS AND APPARATUS:**

- Flat and non-slip surface, at least 30m long.
- Measuring tape of at least 20 meters.
- Marker cones (Big cones and small cones).
- Audio CD or mp3
- CD or mp3 player, Loud speakers.
- Data recording sheets.
- Pen, Pencil, Paper, Writing pad, Cuff sphygmomanometer, Stethoscope, digital weighing scale, Pulse oximeter, Chairs,
- Clothing: comfortable loose-fitting clothing, running shoes with good grip.
- Drink Bottle: some athletes may wish to drink in the recovery area during the yo-yo intermittent tests for occasional small drinks to keep hydrated.

8. **OUTCOME MEASURES:** - Total distance covered (m)

$$VO_2 \text{ Max (mL * kg}^{-1} * \text{min}^{-1})$$

9. **INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- 1) Participants with 18 to 30 years.
- 2) Person who volunteered to participate in the study.

10. **EXCLUSION CRITERIA:**

- 1) Participants with any associated systemic involvement.
- 2) Participants with any neuro-musculoskeletal Problem.
- 3) Participants with any respiratory and cardiovascular disease

11. **Procedure:**

Use cones to mark out two lines 20 meters apart as per the diagram. The subjects start with their foot behind of the lines and begin running when instructed. They continue running between the two lines, turning when signalled by the recorded beeps. After each minute or so, the pace gets quicker. If the line is not reached in time the subject must run to the line turn and try to catch up with the pace within 2 more 'beeps'. The test is stopped if the subject fails to catch up with the pace within the two ends.

Course layout:

Cones or tape is used to mark out the desired course. For the intermittent versions, three parallel lines are needed, two 20 meters apart and another line another 5m (recovery) away from the starting end.

Preparations:

Make sure the participants are adequately prepared well-rested, hydrated and fuelled, and familiar with the test procedure and motivated to perform maximally. Give clear and standardized instructions about the test and what is expected of them including the importance of keeping in time to the recording and completing the full 20m run. Pre-vital signs, Post vital signs (Immediate vitals and After 3 minutes Vital signs) should be taken. Height and weight measurements also can be taken if necessary.

Verbal Instructions for the Yo-Yo Test: -

To ensure good reliability for conducting the yo-yo test, one should provide consistent instructions to the participants prior to conducting the test.

Here is a standard script to use when explaining and introducing the test, particularly for those performing the test for the first time.

Introducing the test: -

“You will be performing the yo-yo intermittent recovery test level 1.”

“The aim of the test is to run as many times as possible back and forth between the markers, following the speeds indicated by the signals on the recording.”

“After each back and forth run, you have ten seconds to jog around the marker placed behind the starting line.”

“It is important that you come to a complete stop at the starting line before you start the next run.”

“The running speed is quite slow in the beginning, but increases rapidly as the test progresses. An increase in speed will be indicated.”

“The first time that you are unable to complete the back and forth run within the given time, you will receive a warning. The next time it occurs, your test is over.”

“Your final speed level, as well as the number of back-and-forth shuttles at that level, is recorded as your score.”

“This is a maximal test, at the end it will be very tiring, and you will need to push yourself as hard as you can to get your best score.”

“Do your best and good luck!”

Starting the Test:

All participants should line up along the starting line. The athletes start with a foot behind the starting line, and begin running when instructed by the audio recording. The athlete turns when signalled by the recorded audio beep at the line 20 meters away, and returns to the starting point. For the endurance test, the athletes continue running in time with the audio signals with no rest period. For the intermittent tests, they walk or jog to the next line and back to come to a complete stop at the starting line again, before starting off with indicated.

During the test:

For the intermittent tests, there is an active recovery period of 5 or 10 seconds between every 40 meters run, during which the subject must walk or jog to the next line and return to the starting point. At regular intervals, the running speed will increase, as indicated on the recording.

Finishing the test:

The participants must continue for as long as they can. Some of the athletes will choose to stop when they have reached their physical limit. For others, one should need to give a warning as they drop behind the required pace or make one of the errors listed below. On the second infraction one should pull them out of the test.

One should give a warning when the participant...

- Starts the run before the audio signal.
- Does not reach either line before the audio signal.
- Turns without touching or going over the line (therefore running short).
- Does not come to a complete stop before starting the next 40m run

Scoring:

The athlete's score is the total distance covered before they were unable to keep up with recording. The Yo-Yo intermittent test usually takes between 6-20 minutes for level 1. The test is comprised of 91 shuttles and can last up to approximately 29-minutes; however, it is very unlikely somebody will complete it.

Scores can be presented in three ways:

- 1) Total distance (meters)
- 2) Level achieved
- 3) VO₂ Max.

Total distance is much simpler to understand, calculate and widely used, whereas level achieved is more complex as the test begins at level 5 and then skips to level 9 at the beginning.

How to: 1. Calculate Total Distance

This is the simplest, most common, and perhaps the most reliable method of reporting YYIR test performance.

To calculate total distance, the simplest method is to record the number of shuttles completed by the participant and then multiply that number by 40 (40 = 2 x 20m shuttles [the run from cone B to cone C = 20m, then run back from cone C to cone B = 20m]).

For example, if an athlete performs 30 shuttles, this number can then be multiplied by 40 to calculate their total distance (e.g., 30 x 40 = 1,200m)

How to: 2. Calculate Level Achieved

To calculate the levels which are achieved by the player is according to the speed is one of the ways to evaluate the test result. (5,9,11,12,13,14 to 23)

It is calculated as the table which is given below;

Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test - Level 1						
Speed Level	Shuttle No.	speed	level time	accumulated shuttle dist	Cumulative Time*	Approx Vo2max
		(km/hr)	(s)	(m)	(s)	(mL/min/kg)
5	1	10	14.4	40	00:24	36.74
9	1	12	12.5	80	00:46	37.07
11	1	13	11.1	120	01:07	37.41
11	2	13	11.1	160	01:29	37.74
12	1	13.5	10.7	200	01:49	38.08
12	2	13.5	10.7	240	02:10	38.42
12	3	13.5	10.7	280	02:31	38.75
13	1	14	10.3	320	02:51	39.09
13	2	14	10.3	360	03:11	39.42
13	3	14	10.3	400	03:31	39.76
13	4	14	10.3	440	03:52	40.10
14	1	14.5	9.9	480	04:12	40.43
14	2	14.5	9.9	520	04:32	40.77
14	3	14.5	9.9	560	04:51	41.10
14	4	14.5	9.9	600	05:11	41.44
14	5	14.5	9.9	640	05:31	41.78
14	6	14.5	9.9	680	05:51	42.11
14	7	14.5	9.9	720	06:11	42.45
14	8	14.5	9.9	760	06:31	42.78
15	1	15	9.6	800	06:51	43.12
15	2	15	9.6	840	07:10	43.46
15	3	15	9.6	880	07:30	43.79
15	4	15	9.6	920	07:50	44.13
15	5	15	9.6	960	08:09	44.46
15	6	15	9.6	1000	08:29	44.80
15	7	15	9.6	1040	08:48	45.14
15	8	15	9.6	1080	09:08	45.47
16	1	15.5	9.3	1120	09:27	45.81
16	2	15.5	9.3	1160	09:47	46.14
16	3	15.5	9.3	1200	10:06	46.48
16	4	15.5	9.3	1240	10:25	46.82
16	5	15.5	9.3	1280	10:44	47.15
16	6	15.5	9.3	1320	11:04	47.49
16	7	15.5	9.3	1360	11:23	47.82
16	8	15.5	9.3	1400	11:42	48.16
17	1	16	9	1440	12:01	48.50
17	2	16	9	1480	12:20	48.83
17	3	16	9	1520	12:39	49.17
17	4	16	9	1560	12:58	49.50
17	5	16	9	1600	13:17	49.84
17	6	16	9	1640	13:36	50.18
17	7	16	9	1680	13:55	50.51
17	8	16	9	1720	14:14	50.85
18	1	16.5	8.7	1760	14:33	51.18
18	2	16.5	8.7	1800	14:52	51.52
18	3	16.5	8.7	1840	15:10	51.86
18	4	16.5	8.7	1880	15:29	52.19
18	5	16.5	8.7	1920	15:48	52.53
18	6	16.5	8.7	1960	16:07	52.86
18	7	16.5	8.7	2000	16:25	53.20
18	8	16.5	8.7	2040	16:44	53.54
19	1	17	8.5	2080	17:03	53.87
19	2	17	8.5	2120	17:21	54.21
19	3	17	8.5	2160	17:39	54.54
19	4	17	8.5	2200	17:58	54.88
19	5	17	8.5	2240	18:16	55.22
19	6	17	8.5	2280	18:35	55.55
19	7	17	8.5	2320	18:53	55.89
19	8	17	8.5	2360	19:12	56.22
20	1	17.5	8.2	2400	19:30	56.56
20	2	17.5	8.2	2440	19:48	56.90
20	3	17.5	8.2	2480	20:07	57.23
20	4	17.5	8.2	2520	20:25	57.57
20	5	17.5	8.2	2560	20:43	57.90
20	6	17.5	8.2	2600	21:01	58.24
20	7	17.5	8.2	2640	21:19	58.58
20	8	17.5	8.2	2680	21:38	58.91
21	1	18	8.0	2720	21:56	59.25
21	2	18	8.0	2760	22:14	59.58
21	3	18	8.0	2800	22:32	59.92
21	4	18	8.0	2840	22:50	60.26
21	5	18	8.0	2880	23:08	60.59
21	6	18	8.0	2920	23:26	60.93
21	7	18	8.0	2960	23:44	61.26
21	8	18	8.0	3000	24:02	61.60
22	1	18.5	7.8	3040	24:19	61.94
22	2	18.5	7.8	3080	24:37	62.27
22	3	18.5	7.8	3120	24:55	62.61
22	4	18.5	7.8	3160	25:13	62.94
22	5	18.5	7.8	3200	25:31	63.28
22	6	18.5	7.8	3240	25:48	63.62
22	7	18.5	7.8	3280	26:06	63.95
22	8	18.5	7.8	3320	26:24	64.29
23	1	19	7.6	3360	26:42	64.62
23	2	19	7.6	3400	26:59	64.96
23	3	19	7.6	3440	27:17	65.30
23	4	19	7.6	3480	27:34	65.63
23	5	19	7.6	3520	27:52	65.97
23	6	19	7.6	3560	28:09	66.30
23	7	19	7.6	3600	28:27	66.64
23	8	19	7.6	3640	28:45	66.98

* Cumulative time includes 10 second recovery period between shuttles

How to: 3. Calculate VO₂ Max

Though the YYIR1 has been shown to be a moderately reliable predictor of VO₂ Max, it is advised to use the test for what it was originally developed for – identifying an individual’s ability to repeatedly perform high-intensity aerobic work, which has proven to be a more sensitive measure of changes in performance than VO₂ Max.

The equations for calculating VO₂ Max are below:

$$\text{YYIR1 test: VO}_2 \text{ Max (mL * kg}^{-1} \text{ * min}^{-1}) = \text{IR1 distance (m)} \times 0.0084 + 36.4$$

Yo-Yo Intermittent Recovery Test - Level 1 Average Results				
Standard of Soccer Player	Men		Women	
	Distance	Level	Distance	Level
Top Elite Players	2420m	20.1	1600m	17.5
Moderate-Elite Players	2190m	19.3	1360m	16.7
Sub-Elite Players	2030m	18.7	1160m	16.2
Moderately Trained Players	1810m	18.2		
Recreational Players	1200-1300m	16.3 - 16.5	600-700m	14.4 - 14.6

Source: Bangsbo et al (2008)

Target population:

This test is suitable sports team and school team groups, but not for populations in which a maximal exercise test would be contraindicated. It is can be performed by elite players, trained players and even in recreational players. In this research the **recreational players** are targeted as population.

Advantages: Large groups can perform this test all at once for minimal costs.

Disadvantages: Practice and motivation levels can influence the score attained, and the scoring of when a person is out of the test can be subjective. As the test is usually conducted outside, the environmental condition can also affect the result. The test CD must be purchased.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result:

Table 1: Group Statistics for VO₂ max of group 1(basketball players) and group 2(cricket players)

	GRP	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
VO2MAX	1.00	34	42.3800	2.28454	.39180
	2.00	34	42.2303	2.70533	.46396

Table 2: Comparison between the significant difference of VO₂Max between group 1(recreational basketball players) and group 2(recreational cricket players)

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means					
F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference

									Lower	Upper
VO2MAX	Equal variances assumed	1.561	.216	.247	66	.806	.14971	.60726	-1.06273	1.36214
	Equal variances not assumed			.247	64.200	.806	.14971	.60726	-1.06336	1.36277

t-test at 95% of confidence interval. There was statistically “No” significant difference found as per maximum oxygen consumption (VO₂Max) between group 1(recreational basketball players) (sig. difference = 0.806) and group 2(recreational cricket players) (sig. difference = 0.806).

Table 3: Group Statistics for total distance covered of group 1(basketball players) and group 2(cricket players)

GRP		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
DISTANCE	1.00	34	711.7647	271.96781	46.64209
	2.00	34	694.1176	322.09652	55.23910

Table4: Comparison between the significant difference of total covered distance between group 1(recreational basketball players) and group 2(recreational cricket players)

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
DISTANCE	Equal variances assumed	1.563	.216	.244	66	.808	17.64706	72.29691	-126.69837	161.99249
	Equal variances not assumed			.244	64.197	.808	17.64706	72.29691	-126.77407	162.06819

t-test is used at 95% of confidence interval. There was statistically “No” significant difference found as per total covered distance between group 1(recreational basketball players) (sig. difference = 0.808) and group 2(recreational cricket players) (sig. difference = 0.808).

DISCUSSION

Usually, the Yo-Yo tests are developed to check and to increase the individual’s ability in their related sports. Yo-Yo tests are more focused and directional towards the fitness of the players who are in the intermittent sports like football, basketball, etc. The Yo-Yo tests are done in different manners as they all have different types in their functions of working. Some of the Yo-Yo tests are able to evaluate the fitness, recovery in between the test shuttles and even the endurance

according how much they covered the distance in test, their estimated VO_2 Max and speed levels which are achieved by them also indicated by these tests.

Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 is one of the types of The Yo-Yo tests. The Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 helps to evaluate the physical and mental fitness of the players who are into this specific shuttle test. Here in this study, Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 type of Yo-Yo test had been taken on recreational basketball and cricket players. Fitness of the players is by far depended on the distance which they covered in their shuttle runs of the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 and VO_2 Max which is maximum oxygen consumption by individual also taken. Secondly, speed level achieved also taken with kilometer per hour measurement in this study. But more focus had been given on the total covered distance and VO_2 Max in this study.

Castagna C. and his team examined that the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 might be considered as a valid basketball-specific test for the assessment of aerobic fitness and game-related endurance.⁸

As far as study on YYIR test level 1 concern, there had been comparative study done between the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 and University of Montreal Track test (UM-TT) by Dupont G. and his team which showed that values of MEV were slightly higher than the peak velocity¹².

The approach of this study was limited to the YYIR test level 1 in recreational basketball players and recreational cricket players. The primary views of significant difference of the test were given to the total covered distance regarding with their estimated maximum oxygen consumption. Yet, this test is pre-set timed stages or pre-set timed beep stages so it is related to the time exhaustion of the individual's test that is why the test had been also viewed as high-intensity intermittent exercise performance.

There is a study which is done on elite junior Australian football players with the Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 to discriminate the group of players in the manner of elite junior players, sub-elite junior players and non-athletic healthy junior players which concluded that elite junior players had significantly greater total covered distance than sub-elite junior players and sub-elite junior players had higher significantly greater total covered distance than non-athletic healthy junior players and lesser total covered distance than elite junior players.¹³

Similarly, the discriminative study of Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 had been done on prospective young football players who are under the age of 19. Discrimination in the study had been done regarding their playing position (forward position, forward-back position, mid-field position, wide mid-field position, defense position) in the game of football. Study concluded that forward position players had significantly better fitness than the other playing positions in football.¹⁴

Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 had been done by participants at their highest physical limit. It showed their physical fitness that push themselves to the next limit and showed more capability. Even in Yo-Yo tests other than Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1, there is another recovery also which shows the fitness ability at the maximum physical limit and that test is Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 2. Level 2 is preferred more in measuring the fitness ability on elite and well-trained intermittent sports players. The Yo-Yo IR2 test was shown to be a sensitive tool to differentiate between intermittent exercise performance of soccer players in different seasonal periods and at different competitive levels and playing positions.¹⁶

YYIR test level 1 is helpful to evaluate the fitness ability like YYIR test level 2. But, the main difference between both test is the starting speeds, so that at any given time the athlete would be running at a faster speed if they are doing the level 2 test compared to the level 1 test. The different levels were originally designed for testing athletes at different playing levels (and therefore it was assumed different fitness levels). If the test was too easy then the athlete would continue for a long time, if too hard, the test would be over too quickly. Different levels were required so athletes of different fitness levels could complete the test in a similar time frame, and consequently similar energy systems would be stressed. Just as the level 1 and level 2 tests are used to test groups of different fitness level, similarly it can be used to test males and females. The levels level one test can be used for women, as women generally have a slower maximum running speed and VO_2 max level, while men do the level 2 test.¹⁸

Generally, the intermittent nature of the yo-yo tests taxes both the aerobic and anaerobic energy system, but the relative contribution of each system will depend on many factors, such as the duration and intensity of the test. Depending on the starting speed and the fitness level and running speed of the athletes being tested, the relative contribution from each energy system will vary.¹²

The Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1 has a high-discriminative ability to distinguish between elite and non-elite young football players.¹⁹

There is one study which showed that this is a specific-valid test for basketball players.⁸

Professional and Semi-professional rugby players were examined with Yo-Yo intermittent recovery test level 1. Total covered distance was taken as the performance index and physiological variables. The performance of the professional rugby players had been measured higher than the semi-professional rugby players. But comparing to the physiological variables with their performance values, there was no significant difference found by Atkins S.J. in the study.²⁰

CONCLUSION

- This study states that there is no significant difference between total distance covered and VO₂ max in recreational cricket and basketball players.
- A significant difference could have been found in elite players compared to recreational players.
- So, for future study same test can be performed on elite players as well as other parameters such as levels achieved, heart rate, blood pressure, SPO₂ can be taken into consideration.

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